

Raw Data

Structure of data folder:

\behavioral_data folder contains 22 subfolders storing the full raw behavioral data for each rat trained on the task described in the manuscript ("Rats spontaneously perceive global motion direction of drifting plaids"). Within each rat folder the data of all training and priming behavioral sessions can be found inside the \Extracted folder as individual matfiles. The naming convention for matfiles is the following: data of non priming (i.e. training) sessions are stored in files named *Ratname*_*Date*_*Group*_extr (e.g. "BZ3_18_02_28_Grating_extr") whereas data of priming sessions are stored in files named *Ratname*_*Date*_*Group*Prime_extr (e.g. "BZ3_18_02_28_GratingPrime_extr"). \Extracted folders also contain matfiles already aggregating data from multiple sessions in a single file.

Important variables list:

session_id = session identity number
ignored = boolean for the ignored trials whinin the current session (1 = ignored)
success = boolean for the successful trials whinin the current session (1 = success)
failed = boolean for the incorrect trials whinin the current session (1 = failure)
resp_time = animal response time for each trial (from the target onset, in ms)
stim_time = timing of current trial the target onset (from session start, in ms)
prime_id = prime identity (0 = identity prime, 1 = cross prime)
prime_direction = direction of prime in degrees, with 0° indicating global direction = right and 180° indicating global direction = left
stim_direction = code for the target direction (1 = left and 2 = right)

Idealized simulation

Script list:

idealized_simulation.m

This script reproduce an idealized simulation of a grating/plaid direction discrimination task as the one performed by the animals in in the experiment described in the manuscript ("Rats spontaneously perceive global motion direction of drifting plaids"). The aim of this simulation is to check the consistency of the priming curves observed for the plaid group with a pattern-based representation of global motion direction. This script can reproduce the results displayed in Fig4, FigS2 and FigS3 of the paper.

Function list:

```
generate_representation.m  
regularized_cost_function.m  
sigmoid.m  
predict.m  
vmf.m
```

Running Instructions:

Run `idealized_simulation.m`.

Detailed simulation

```
detailed_simulation.m
```

This script runs a more physiologically detailed simulation of the grating vs plaid direction discrimination task performed by animals in the experiment described in the manuscript ("Rats spontaneously perceive global motion direction of drifting plaids"). The aim of this simulation is to explore the mechanisms that could lead to a strong cross-priming only in case of training with plaid stimuli (scenario #1 and #2). This script can reproduce the results displayed in Fig5, Fig6 and FigS4 of the paper.

Function list:

```
circ_vmpdf.m  
compute_osi_and_dsi.m  
dsi2of.m  
of2dsi.m  
get_population_response.m  
kappa_osi_lookup_table.mat  
kappa2osi.m  
osi2kappa.m  
population_diagnostics.m  
regularized_cost_function.m  
sigmoid.m  
predict.m  
sample_poisson_response.m  
wrap2circle_zero.m
```

Running Instructions:

Run `detailed_simulation.m`. With different settings of the variables `scenario2_bool` and `chosen_suppression_type_index` it's possible to reproduce the different scenarios described in the paper. Edit `scenario_2_bool` variable (line 32) to switch from scenario #1 to scenario #2 (0 => "scenario #1" and 1 => "scenario #2"). While keeping `scenario_2_bool = 0` edit `chosen_suppression_type_index` (line 48) to reproduce control experiment for the necessity of asymmetric cross orientation suppression (1 = no suppression, 2 = symmetric suppression, 3 = asymmetric suppression).

Behavioral Analysis

Script list:

`learning_curves_data_extraction_and_aggregation.m`

This script extracts and aggregates the raw training sessions data for the training data to generate learning curves for all rats. The aim of the analysis subsequently carried out on learning curves is to show the time course of learning for target discrimination for the two groups of rats. This script reproduces the results displayed in Fig2 of the paper.

`data_extraction_and_aggregation.m`

This script extracts and aggregates the raw priming sessions data. It also performs the bootstrap sample generation for the subsequent analysis.

`group_average_and_selection.m`

This script performs the selection of rats to include in the analysis for each group and, then, computes the full data group averages, including: priming curves, priming magnitudes and neural performance differences.

`group_average_bootstrap.m`

This script computes group averages for the priming curves, the priming magnitude and the neural performance differences for each bootstrap sample considering only the selected rats.

`combine_bootstrap_results.m`

This script uses all bootstrap samples to get bootstrap standard deviations and confidence intervals for group averages (including priming curves, priming magnitudes and neural performance differences). The aim of this analysis is to show the effects of prime stimuli

direction and identity on target discrimination performance for the two groups of rats. This script reproduces the results displayed in Fig3 and FigS1 of the paper.

Function list:

```
get_prime_effect_magnitude.m  
plot_shaded_mu_std.m  
set_parameters_and_metadata.m  
get_ones_seqs.m
```

Running Instructions:

Run scripts in the following order:

1. `learning_curves_data_extraction_and_aggregation`: to generate and plot the learning curves together with related quantifications.
2. `data_extraction_and_aggregation` (setting at line 17 `bool_bootstrap_resample = 0`): to generate bootstrap sample data aggregates.
3. `data_extraction_and_aggregation` (setting at line 17 `bool_bootstrap_resample = 1`): to generate full data aggregates.
4. `group_average_and_selection`: to select rats reaching the criteria for inclusion in the analysis and compute group averages (priming curves, priming magnitudes and neural performance differences) for the complete dataset.
5. `group_average_bootstrap`: to compute group averages (priming curves, priming magnitudes and neural performance differences) over all selected rats for each bootstrap sample.
6. `combine_bootstrap_results`: to compute bootstrap standard deviation, perform statistical tests and plot priming curves together with related qualifications.